

10 GHz Optoelectronic Circuit with Variable Sigmoid Shaped Activation Function for Photonic Neural Networks

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Abstract— This paper introduces an opto-electronic and opto-electronic-opto circuit capable of generating a Sigmoid shaped non-linear activation function (NLAF) for photonic neural networks. The main element of the circuit is a III-V photonic integrated circuit featuring an O-band semiconductor optical amplifier (SOA) co-integrated with a uni-travelling carrier photodiode, connected to a Bi-CMOS transimpedance amplifier (TIA). Experimental results from two 10 GHz 32-level mirrored step-wise pulse sequences, and three 30-level random peak power pulse sequences, validate the proposed concept, showcasing the variation of the achieved sigmoid NLAF from nearly stepwise to linear by appropriately varying the SOA current, injection of an external CW signal and proper configuration of the TIA settings.

Index Terms— Opto-electronic, Sigmoid activation function, Non-linear activation function, Photonic Neural Networks, Optical Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

PHOTONIC neural networks (PNNs) are a novel computing architecture technology that harnesses the unique properties of light to perform ultra-fast and energy-efficient computations [1]. Utilizing the expansive bandwidth and minimal propagation loss characteristics of integrated photonic platforms [2], integrated PNNs present a promising avenue for realizing notable benefits in comparison to conventional electronic hardware [3]. Specifically, PNNs hold the capacity to perform vector matrix multiplications (VMMs) at frequencies reaching tens of GHz, all while maintaining minimal power consumption. This feature renders PNNs well-suited for applications that require real-time processing of large amounts of complex data, such as image [4], 3D area [5], recognition and network traffic analysis [6].

The implementation of PNNs comprises multiple layers of VMM units interconnected via nonlinear activation function (NLAF) modules. The output of each NLAF drives the next

linear layer, with the final layer implementing the NN's classification result. So far though, the NLAF elements for most PNN are implemented in the digital domain [1], [2], [7], that comes in conjunction with high speed SerDes circuits imposing significant energy and latency overheads [8]. Therefore, analog high speed photonic NLAFs are critical elements for achieving the envisaged high performance and energy efficiency in large-scale multi layered PNNs. The first efforts to demonstrate sigmoid-shaped transfer functions focused on exploiting the nonlinear gain of semiconductor optical amplifiers (SOAs) for 2R signal regeneration [9]–[11]. However, it is essential to recognize that in the context of optical neural networks, the emphasis lies on achieving reconfigurability in terms of steepness in the transfer function, as this adaptability allows for task-specific optimization in each instance [12]–[14]. Towards this direction, several analog electro-optic (EO) and all-optical (OO) nonlinear activation functions, have been demonstrated for achieving the NLAF in the optical realm [8], [12], [22], [23], [13], [15]–[21], exploiting micro-ring resonators, photonic crystals, and phase change materials. These successfully implemented a diverse set of activation functions commonly employed in digital neural networks, such as sigmoid [13], [15]–[17], [19], ReLU [8], [12], [13], [17]–[20], tanh [8], [13] and PreLU-like [16]. Notably, some of these demonstrations have also incorporated programmability by using a single building block to realize a diverse set of activation functions [12], [13], [16]–[19], [22], [23]. This feature provides the flexibility to select or optimize activation biases, enabling the PNN to be applied across a broader spectrum of machine learning tasks without requiring hardware modifications [24].

Another category with unique OE and OO non-linear activation is the spiking photonic neural networks (SPNN) [25]–[28]. However, their training models are not as effective as classical deep learning networks, limiting their applicability in supporting photonic accelerators designed for conventional

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deep learning models. Additionally, implementing SPNNs requires expensive specialized hardware that is less readily available compared to the infrastructure required for non-spiking continued-valued neural networks.

Towards more advanced PNNs with improved performance, several researchers have also introduced innovative nonlinear functions [29]–[32], showing remarkable potential in supporting high-accuracy DNN models. These are mainly characterized by their analog nature, while recent studies have highlighted their superior performance in PNNs compared to the legacy ones commonly used in DNNs [14]. A notable example is the photonic sigmoid NLA [15], that exhibited significant performance advantages when replacing the widely adopted ReLU in optical channel equalization tasks [33]. This theoretical work in tandem with its experimental validation [34], revealed significantly improved BER performance in End-to-End DL-based IM/DD transmission links regarding noise and dispersion tolerance.

Unfortunately, the current implementations of the photonic sigmoid in the optical domain are either limited to low-speed deployments [13], or rely on bulky fiber-pigtailed Mach-Zehnder interferometer-based all-optical circuits [15], hindering their integration into large scale PNNs targeting applications in commercial environments. Therefore, there is a demand for compact and multi GHz photonic sigmoid NLA circuitry that can be seamlessly integrated into PNN architectures and at the same time relax the stringent power budget requirements of multi-layer PNNs. Finally, the ability to adjust the slope of the sigmoid NLA, ranging from step-wise to almost linear, would be a significant advantage towards deploying versatile and programmable NLA modules.

In this paper, we extend our previous work [35], on a compact opto-electronic (OE) and an opto-electronic-opto (OEO) NLA circuit capable of providing an adjustable slope sigmoid-shaped NLA operating at a computing rate of 10 GHz. The OE NLA circuit comprises a III-V photonic integrated circuit (PIC) co-integrating an O-band SOA with a

uni-traveling carrier (UTC) photodiode (PD), assembled with a BiCMOS SiGE technology electronic integrated circuit (EIC) consisting of an electronically controlled transimpedance amplifier (TIA), on a single PCB. The OEO NLA circuit extends the capabilities of the OE NLA circuit, wherein its electrical output is directed into a modulator via a linear RF amplifier. This arrangement serves to illustrate the process of supplying a subsequent photonics neural layer by reconverting the electrical signal into optical. Experimental investigation of the proposed circuits using a 10 GHz 32-level step-wise pulse sequence and three 30-level pulse analog waveform with random peak power validated the proper functionality of the circuitry, allowing the variation of the achieved sigmoid function from nearly stepwise to linear by controlling the SOA current, injection of an external CW signal and proper configuration of the TIA settings. The NLA circuitry consumed 250 mW to 360 mW, depending on the TIA and SOA settings, while investigation of the electro-optic bandwidth of the NLA circuitry revealed an S_{21} 3 dB bandwidth exceeding 40 GHz. These measurements highlight the potential of the proposed module to operate at baud rates of up to 40 Gbaud and an energy envelope ranging from 6.2 pJ/bit to 9 pJ/bit establishing it as a valuable component for multi-layer PNNs and signal processing systems. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the NLA OE circuit assembly and the experimental setup, Section III presents results of the OE and OEO NLA, Section IV presents a discussion about the performance of the circuit, and Section V summarizes the paper.

II. CIRCUIT DESCRIPTION, PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION AND EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP.

Figure 1(a) depicts a microscope photo of the OE NLA circuitry. The circuit comprises a PIC assembled with an EIC. The PIC comprises an InP O-band 700 μm long pre-amplifier SOA co-integrated monolithically with a high-speed UTC-PD measuring $5 \times 25 \mu\text{m}^2$ [36]. The UTC-PD is wire bonded to the

Fig. 1. (a) Top view microscope photo of the opto-electronic circuit, consisting of the SOA-UTC-PD integrated pre-amplifier receiver on the photonic integrated circuit, wire bonded to the electronic integrated circuit TIA. Each component used in the experiment is highlighted with the dashed lines. (b) Experimental set up for the circuitry characterization to get the OE (A-red arrow), and OEO (B-red arrow) transfer function. LD: Laser diode, AWG: Arbitrary waveform generator, RFA: RF amplifier, MOD: Modulator, PDFFA: Praseodymium doped fiber amplifier, OBPF: Optical bandpass filter, VOA: Variable optical attenuator, CO: Coupler, CIR: Circulator, PM: Power Meter, OSA: Optical spectrum analyzer, SOA: Semiconductor optical amplifier, UTC-PD: Uni-traveling-carrier photodiode, TIA: Transimpedance amplifier, DCB: DC block, RTO: Real-time oscilloscope.

Fig. 2. (a) Amplified spontaneous emission spectrum of the SOA captured at the InP chip edge for different SOA operating current ranging from 30 mA to 150 mA. (b) S_{21} parameters of the NLAf OE circuit for TIA settings 1 and 2 (TS1 and TS2) and SOA current operating current of 60 mA and (c) 90 mA.

one channel of a quad-channel TIA EIC fabricated in a 55 nm SiGe-BiCMOS technology [37]. The signal is collectable from the TIA via two differential outputs in GSSG configuration accessible by an RF probe. The III-V PIC and the TIA EIC are mounted on a PCB connecting the SOA, the UTC-PD, and the TIA with the required external power supplies. Moreover, dedicated electrical pads on the PCB enable the seamless control of the integrated electronic registers of the TIA via an external computer.

The activation function of the OE NLAf circuit results from the combined gain response of the SOA UTC-PD chip and the TIA. The SOA receives optical power and amplifies it linearly or non-linearly depending on the input power level. The additional optical CW signals from LD2 reduce the number of carriers available for amplification, effectively clamping the gain and shifting the saturation point to lower input power. The UTC-PD converts the optical signal into a photocurrent at its output and depending again on its level, the TIA operates in the linear or clipped non-linear regime. In addition, by adjusting the parameters of the TIA the gain bandwidth product through the loop gain can be altered inducing a more linear or peaked frequency response. These are the two main sources of linearity of the OE circuit. In terms of mathematical description, the responsivity of the III-V chip as measured in [36], follows an exponential equation similar to the gain of the SOA [38]–[40]. On the other part the output voltage of the TIA versus input current follows a tanh-like shape function according to [14]. For the complete OEO circuit, where the optical Mach Zehnder Modulator (MZM) is cascaded for the optical conversion, a third source of non-linearity is introduced, described by the squared sinusoidal response of the interferometer.

It should be noted that the proposed OE circuit imposes a NLAf based on the amplitude of the electric field of the incoming optical signal. Therefore, it is compatible in principle with any photonic multiply-accumulate (MAC) architecture that employs amplitude modulation to encode the summation information. As such, the circuitry can be seamlessly integrated with typical coherent MAC units [6], [41]. In scenarios where the circuit is employed within wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) architectures, where summation of multi-wavelength signals occurs at the PD, the proper circuit operation necessitates calibration addressing the wavelength gain and responsivity dependencies of both the SOA and the PD, respectively.

Figure 1(b) illustrates the experimental set up employed for the evaluation of the OE NLAf circuit and is labelled as scenario A by following the red arrow. The signal for the

evaluation of the circuit with the NLAf is emitted by a laser diode (LD) 1 at 1310 nm connected to a 40 GHz bandwidth LiNbO₃ modulator (MOD), driven by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) operating at a sampling rate up to 100 GS/s. The output of MOD1 is amplified by the O-band praseodymium doped fiber amplifier (PDFA) delivering 14 dBm average optical power. Subsequently the signal passes through an optical band pass filter (OBPF) with a bandwidth of 0.5 nm to reject out-of-band amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise. The power of the signal injected to the circuit is adjusted by a variable optical attenuator (VOA) and connected afterwards to one input of a 3 dB coupler (CO). At this point, the modulated signal is combined with a CW signal coming from LD 2 at 1312 nm that acts as a holding beam towards adjusting the SOA's gain and recovery time. Both signals then pass through a circulator (CIR) and are injected to the SOA via a lensed fiber with 2.5 μ m spot size. The CIR also serves for capturing the SOA's ASE spectrum. The output of the TIA was accessed through a DC-40 GHz bandwidth GS probe and captured at the 66 GHz bandwidth real time oscilloscope (RTO) featuring 160 GS/s sampling rate. For the protection of the RTO, a DC block is inserted in the line since the TIA operates at 2-3 Volts DC levels. In scenario B also highlighted in Fig. 1(b), where the goal was to demonstrate the feeding of a subsequent photonics neural layer by converting the electrical signal back to optical, the output of the TIA was injected into MOD2 using a linear RF amplifier with a bandwidth of 40 GHz and maximum 5.6 V_{pp} output. The output of MOD2 was then captured using a 70 GHz bandwidth PD connected to the RTO.

Figure 2(a) displays the ASE spectra recorded for different injection currents at the SOA at the edge of the PIC with the CIR, revealing that after 120 mA the ASE power is saturated with no significant gain observed for higher input currents. Fig. 2(b), (c) present the S_{21} curves of the entire NLAf OE circuit up to 50 GHz, for 60 mA and 90 mA driving currents to the SOA, -2 dBm input optical power and two different set of settings of the TIA i.e. TIA settings 1 (TS1) and TIA settings (TS2). The two TIA configurations differentiated by controlling integrated control registers. The parameters tuned from TS1 to TS2 include a) adjusted the input stage bias current from 8.8 mA to 6.4 mA, reducing the input stage's loop gain and subsequently diminishing input stage gain and bandwidth, b) modifying the degeneration resistor from 6.7 Ohm to 18.5 Ohm, thereby enhancing linearity and, c) altering the bias current of the output stage from 12 mA to 7.2 mA, resulting in reduced output stage gain and signal swing. Overall, transitioning from

Fig. 3. (a) “Normal” waveform injected into the OE NLAf circuit through the SOA. TIA output waveforms captured at different operating conditions, for TIA settings 1 (TS1) (b) $I_{SOA} = 60$ mA without CW, (c) $I_{SOA} = 60$ mA with 3 dBm CW, (d) $I_{SOA} = 90$ mA without CW, (e) $I_{SOA} = 90$ mA with 3 dBm CW, and for TIA setting 2 (TS2) (f) $I_{SOA} = 60$ mA without CW, (g) 60 mA with 3 dBm CW, (h) $I_{SOA} = 90$ mA without CW, (i) $I_{SOA} = 90$ mA with 3 dBm CW. Horizontal-axis is Time in Samples (6.25 ps/Sample). The red curve depicts the envelope formed by the pulse peak values of the sequence. I_{SOA} : SOA drive current.

TS1 to TS2 is yielding a reduction in gain and increased linearity across the entire DC-40 GHz frequency span.

Comparison of the S21 curve for both TIA settings, reveals that for 90 mA there is approximately a 5 dB more gain versus 60 mA at 10 GHz. The overall bandwidth of the OE circuit is more than 40 GHz and the sharp cutoff after this frequency is due to the K-connector of the GS probe for both cases.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Characterization of the circuit with step-wise pulse sequences

The adjustable NLAf of the circuit was determined by injecting to the SOA, two custom 32-level pulse waveforms, totaling 64 symbols. Each pulse had a duration of 100 ps, allowing evaluation of the circuit at 10 GHz. The first sequence referred to as “normal” and shown in Fig. 3(a) started from the lowest pulse peak power level of 0 mW and incrementally increased to 2 mW. On the other hand, the second sequence, referred to as “inverse” and illustrated in Fig. 4(a), started from the highest power level of 2 mW, and decreased to 0 mW. The purpose of testing the circuit with these two mirrored pulse sequences was to determine if there were any memory or pattern effects

originating from the SOA's gain-limited recovery time at this rate. Both sequences feature “positive” and “negative” pulses around the 1 mW power level, that were transformed into positive and negative voltages at the RTO due to the DC block placed in the transmission line. In this rationale, peak powers above 1 mW corresponded to positive input values, while peak power below 1 mW represented negative input values for the circuit. Consequently the 1 mW power level was serving as the equivalent of the DC level and the peak power step between the 32 levels was 65 μ W step. Additionally, the co-propagating CW light injected from LD2 introducing another axis of freedom towards the SOA's gain and recovery time, besides modifying the SOA's injection current. The NLAf was further adjusted by changing the settings of the TIA between two sets of parameters TS1 and TS2 with the overall change in the transfer function of the OE circuit shown in Fig. 2(b) and Fig. 2(c). The electrical signal at the TIA's output was captured by the RTO for subsequent post-processing. After exploring various combinations of operational conditions, the driving current of the SOA was set to either 60 mA or 90 mA, since at 30 mA, the gain was very low, and at 120 mA, the gain benefit was rather marginal. The input power from LD2 to the InP chip could either be 2 mW or switched off completely. Concludingly the

Fig. 4. (a) “Inverse” waveform injected into the OE NLAf circuit through the SOA. TIA output waveforms captured at different operating conditions, for TIA settings 1 (TS1) (b) $I_{SOA} = 60$ mA without CW, (c) $I_{SOA} = 60$ mA with 3 dBm CW, (d) $I_{SOA} = 90$ mA without CW, (e) $I_{SOA} = 90$ mA with 3 dBm CW, and for TIA settings 2 (TS2) (f) $I_{SOA} = 60$ mA without CW, (g) 60 mA with 3 dBm CW, (h) $I_{SOA} = 90$ mA without CW, (i) $I_{SOA} = 90$ mA with 3 dBm CW. Horizontal-axis is Time in Samples (6.25 ps/Sample). The red curve depicts the envelope formed by the pulse peak values of the sequence. I_{SOA} : SOA drive current.

Fig. 5. DUT Transfer function measured at the TIA output for the “normal” black-squares and the “inverse” red-circles for TIA Settings 1 (TS1) (a)-(d) and TIA settings 2 (TS2) (e)-(h) and different SOA gain operating conditions. (a) OC_A, (b) OC_B, (c) OC_C, (d) OC_D, (e) OC_E, (f) OC_F, (g) OC_G, (h) OG_H. The blue line represents the sigmoid fitting on Eq(1) for the combined normal and inverse points.

following eight operation conditions (OC) were examined: (i) OC_A is for 60 mA injection current at the SOA and TS1, (ii) OC_B is for 60 mA applied current to the SOA plus 3 dBm extra CW light from LD2 and TS1, (iii) OC_C is for 90 mA at the SOA and TS1, (iv) OC_D is for 90 mA applied current to the SOA plus 3 dBm extra CW light from LD2 and TS1, (v) OC_E is when 60 mA is injected to the SOA and TS2 are applied, (vi) OC_F is for 60 mA applied to the SOA plus 3 dBm extra CW from LD2 and TS2 are applied, (vii) OC_G is for 90 mA to the SOA and TS2 and finally (viii) OC_H is for 90 mA at the SOA, additional 3 dBm external CW signal and TS2.

Fig.3 (b)-(i) depicts the signal recorded at the TIA output for the “normal” injected waveform recorded under the different operation conditions corresponding from OC_A to OC_H, respectively. Fig.4 (b)-(i) shows the same signals recorded from the TIA output, but for the “inverse” injected waveform under the same operation condition OC_A to OC_H. The red curve on all graphs corresponds to the envelope formed by the pulse peak power that is considered for the extraction of the variable NLAf under the different settings.

It should be noted that the input data were encoded in the fashion of a Return-to-Zero (RZ) waveform, where each input pulse had a distinct peak power, followed by a sample at the intermediate power level, effectively producing the DC level at the TIA output. This DC level is considered analogous to the zero-level in an RZ encoding scheme. Consequently,

measurements taken during these intermediate samples can be disregarded as they do not provide any meaningful information. This approach, through proper sampling, prevents the miscalculation of peak power between the top or bottom sides of the pulses.

Examining the waveforms presented in Fig. 3(b)-(i) in detail, there is a plateau around the minimum and maximum voltage values, corresponding to the lower and higher input peak power levels shown in Fig. 3(a). The total voltage swing and the voltage plateau depend, as expected, on the circuit's overall operation conditions. When comparing the TIA output waveforms between OC_B and OC_D, it is observed that at a bias of 90 mA, the waveform exhibits a higher total voltage swing and faster step-up for the same input power. This aligns with the expected higher gain of the SOA, that delivers more power to the UTC-PD. This is more emphasized for low power pulses, where the SOA operates in the linear regime. The presence of the 3 dBm co-propagating CW light, as evident in Fig. 3(c) and Fig. 3(e), reduces the SOA's gain and, consequently, the total output voltage swing. Additionally, the saturation point is reached in more steps compared to the case without the CW holding beam. Regarding the comparison between TS1 and TS2 under the same SOA gain conditions, TS1 provides a higher voltage swing, while TS2 offers better symmetry between positive and negative peak power voltages.

The “inverse” waveforms in Fig. 4(b)-(i) exhibit a similar response to those in Fig. 3(b)-(i). Once again, there is a plateau

Table I: Sigmoid fitting Parameters of OE TF (TIA output)

Conditions	Figure	A ₁	A ₂	A ₂ + A ₁	A ₁ - A ₂	X ₀	d _x	R ²	10-90% ΔP [mW]
OC_A	5(a)	-175.1	276.0	451.1	100.9	1.064	0.180	0.994	0.791
OC_B	5(b)	-156.4	260.1	416.5	103.7	1.166	0.306	0.990	0.580
OC_C	5(c)	-182.7	269.4	452.1	86.7	1.005	0.132	0.994	1.344
OC_D	5(d)	-165.3	275.8	441.1	110.5	1.145	0.260	0.993	1.142
OC_E	5(e)	-170.4	165.0	335.4	5.4	0.914	0.159	0.996	0.698
OC_F	5(f)	-183.2	183.5	366.7	0.3	0.927	0.375	0.998	0.496
OC_G	5(g)	-170.6	156.1	326.7	14.5	0.895	0.113	0.994	1.647
OC_H	5(h)	-170.0	174.5	344.5	4.5	0.939	0.260	0.997	1.142

Fig. 6. (a) DUT Transfer function sigmoid fitting of equation (1) for different operating conditions (I_{SOA} and co-propagative CW) for TIA settings 1 (TS1) and (b) TIA settings 2 (TS2). d_x determines the steepness of the function at x_0 .

around the minimum and maximum voltage values, corresponding to the low and high input power levels, respectively, as shown in Fig. 4(a). Similar to the "normal" waveforms, the total voltage swing and plateau power limits depend on the circuit's operation conditions. When comparing the "normal" and "inverse" TIA output waveforms under the same operation conditions, both waveforms show similar voltage levels for the same input peak power, crossing through ~ 0 V for 1 mW input power. The pulse amplitudes are clipped at the highest and lowest input peak powers due to the saturation of the SOA and TIA gain.

The power consumption of the SOA for 60 mA and 90 mA driving current was 112 mW and 220 mW respectively. The power consumption of the TIA under TS1 was 139.4 mW and for TS2 136.9 mW. The energy efficiency for the 10 GHz waveforms was calculated ranging from 24.8 pJ/bit up to 35.9 pJ/bit.

For the extraction of the circuit's transfer function, the red curves in Fig. 3(a) and Fig. 4(a) indicate the envelope formed by the peak power of the 32 levels employed as input amplitudes. Similarly, the red envelope curves in Fig. 3(b)-(i) and Fig. 4(b)-(i) represent the peak output amplitude considered for calculating the NLAf of the circuit.

Figure 5 presents the pulse peak power points for both "normal" and "inverse" sequences in the same graph, revealing that the memory effect from the SOA's limited recovery time is quite limited, since for all examined operation conditions, the deviation in the peak output power between the "normal" and "inverse" patterns is almost negligible. Specifically, Fig. 5(a) displays the results for OC_A, Fig. 5(b) to OC_B, Fig. 5(c) to OC_C, and Fig. 5(d) to OC_D. Similarly, Fig. 5(e)-(h) illustrates the points used for calculating the NLAf under TS2, with Fig. 5(e) showing the results for OC_E, Fig. 5(f) for OC_F, Fig. 5(g) for OC_G, and Fig. 5(h) for OC_H. The blue line represents the curve fitting from the combined "normal" and "inverse" points, coming to the logistic sigmoid function expressed mathematically as:

$$f(x) = A_2 + \frac{A_1 - A_2}{1 + e^{\frac{x - x_0}{d_x}}} \quad (1)$$

Where the parameters A_1 and A_2 represent the bottom and top amplitude levels, respectively. The parameter x_0 corresponds to the input peak power at the half width of the total amplitude swing, while d_x determines the steepness of the function at x_0 . The fitting parameters for all sigmoid curves in Fig. 5 are presented in Table I. Notably, the R^2 values of the

sigmoid fitting exceed 0.99 for all cases, indicating a high level of confidence in the chosen function.

Figure 6 displays the fitted NLAf acquired in Fig. 5, grouped according to each TIA setting, with TS1 illustrated in Fig. 6(a), while Fig. 6(b) presents the corresponding curves for TS2. For OC_A, the lower peak amplitude is -175 mV and the upper one 276 mV, resulting in a total voltage swing of 451 mV. The 10% to 90% range of the transfer function corresponds to input peak power values of 0.668 mW and 1.459 mW, respectively, with a transition of $\Delta P = 0.791$ mW. Increasing the SOA bias current to 90 mA leads to a decrease in the upper amplitude limit to 269 mV, an increase in the lower amplitude of -182 mV and a slight increase in the total voltage swing of 452 mV. In this case, the 10% and 90% points of the NLAf correspond to 0.714 mW and 1.295 mW, respectively for a ΔP transition of 0.580 mW. Introducing the additional CW signal to limit the SOA gain at 60 mA results in a reduction of the lower and upper amplitude limits to -156 mV and 260 mV. The 10% point of the NLAf corresponds to an input peak power of 0.493 mW, while the 90% - point equals to 1.938 mW, resulting in a transition width of 1.344 mW. Similarly, for the case of 90 mA SOA biasing with the additional CW, the lower amplitude limit decreases to -165 mV, the upper amplitude increases to 275 mV and the total voltage swing is reduced to 441 mV. The 10% to 90% range of the NLAf corresponds to input peak power values of 0.573 mW and 1.716 mW, respectively, resulting in a transition width of 1.142 mW. The steepness of the TF is inversely proportional to the value of the d_x parameter presented in all cases in Table I and agree very well with the ΔP values presented above. What is important to note is that the gain of the SOA only slightly influences the total output voltage swing, which varies from 452 mV for 90 mA biasing without CW to 416 mV for 60 mA biasing with additional CW. The A_1 and A_2 values also confirm the high asymmetry between positive and negative pulse voltages.

For TS2 and 60 mA SOA biasing without additional CW, the upper and lower peak amplitudes are -170 mV and 165 mV, respectively, resulting in a total voltage swing of 335 mV. The 10% and 90% points of the NLAf correspond to input peak power values of 0.564 mW and 1.263 mW, respectively, with a transition width of $\Delta P = 0.698$ mW. Increasing the SOA bias current to 90 mA maintains the lower amplitude limit at -170 mV, while reducing the upper amplitude limit to 156 mV. The total voltage swing slightly decreases to 326 mV, and the 10% and 90% points of the NLAf correspond to input peak power values of 0.646 mW and 1.143 mW, respectively, resulting in a transition width of 0.496 mW. This case corresponds to the steepest sigmoid NLAf confirmed also by the d_x value in Table I. Introducing additional CW to limit the SOA gain at 60 mA increases the lower and upper amplitude limits to -183 mV and 183 mV, respectively, providing a perfect symmetry for positive and negative voltages. The 10% point of the NLAf corresponds to an input peak power of 0.103 mW, while the 90% point corresponds to 1.750 mW, resulting in a transition width of 1.647 mW. This is the most linear fitted Sigmoid NLAf from all examined operation conditions. Similarly, for the case of 90 mA SOA biasing with additional CW, the lower amplitude limit remains at -170 mV, while the upper amplitude increases to 174 mV. The total voltage swing increases now to 344 mV, and the 10% to 90% range of the

Fig. 7. Random waveform “A” at chip input (blue) and corresponding correlated TIA output (orange) for (a) OC_F and (b) OC_G, horizontal-axis is Time in Samples (6.25 ps/Sample). Experimental input power vs TIA output voltage for (c) OC_F and (d) OC_G. The three waveforms “A” (green), “B” (red), “C” (blue) are fitted with the sigmoid function (black-line) from all experimental data. Y-error distribution between the TIA output experimental data vs the TIA output expected, for OC_F (d) and OC_G (e) respectively.

NLAF corresponds to input peak power values of 0.367 mW and 1.510 mW, respectively, resulting in a transition width of 1.142 mW. Overall, the TS2 setting provides a more symmetric output at the expense of lower voltage swing. It should be noted that in the results presented so far only half of the signal power is collected from the GS output of the TIA, as the other half is emitted from the SG pads that could not be collected due to the lack of the proper RF probe. The two graphs of Fig. 6 reveal an OE circuit that can generate a sigmoid activation function with variable steepness by interplaying with the SOA’s biasing current and an external CW signal. The high output voltage swing is also capable of directly driving the next stage of a PNN.

B. OE NLAF circuit evaluation under random input sequences

To verify the performance of the OE NLAF circuit under random input sequences, three non-deterministic random waveform patterns were injected into the circuit featuring a random shuffling of 30 different input pulse power levels with 100 ps duration. Among the eight operational conditions, only OC_F and OC_G were chosen for this test. The decision was based on two considerations: firstly, TS2 demonstrated a more balanced output around the DC voltage compared to TS1; secondly, in the preceding section, OC_F and OC_G exhibited the lowest and highest steepness, according to the d_x parameter values listed in Table I.

Fig. 7(a) and Fig. 7(b) present the random shuffled waveform “A” at the chip input (blue) and the corresponding correlated TIA output (orange) for OC_F and OC_G respectively. The graphs for waveforms “B” and “C” are omitted since they do

not provide additional information regarding the methodology for extracting the transfer function. The comparison between the blue and orange waveforms at specific time samples, corresponding to the time-shuffled peak power levels, resulted in the data points shown in the graphs of Fig. 7(c) and Fig. 7(d). In these two figures, the three distinct waveforms exhibit similar responses regarding the NLAF shape, with their scatter points distributed with minimal deviation from the mean value. By grouping all points together for each OC, a sigmoid shaped fitting can be applied with the corresponding parameters listed in the following Table II. A comparison with the values of Table I reveals that the d_x parameters are nearly identical for both shuffled and non-shuffled waveforms. The A_1 , A_2 and X_0 , ΔP exhibit though some small discrepancies that can be attributed to the arbitrary time dependent peak power of the pulses.

To further investigate and quantify the accuracy of the sigmoid fitting, Fig. 7(e-f) illustrate the probability density function (PDF) histograms of the Y_{error} distribution for OC_F and OC_G respectively, with Y_{error} defined as:

$$Y_{error} = 100 \times \left(\frac{Y_{exp} - Y_{theo}}{Y_{theo}} \right) \quad (2)$$

where Y_{exp} is the experimental TIA output and Y_{theo} is the TIA output calculated from the sigmoid fitting for the same input power levels. The resulting histogram data are subsequently fitted with a gaussian distribution revealing mean values of 0.47 %, 1.53 % and standard deviation values of 12.9 %, 19.7 % for OC_F and OC_G, respectively. All these values led to the conclusion that the OE NLAF of the circuit is performing as expected and calculated for the step-wise waveforms in

Table II: Sigmoid fitting Parameters of OE TF for random shuffled waveform (TIA output)

Conditions	Figure	A_1	A_2	$A_2+ A_1 $	$ A_1 - A_2 $	X_0	d_x	R^2	10-90% ΔP [mw]
OC_F	7(c)	-170.0	189.1	359.1	19.1	0.975	0.3951	0.994	1.323
OC_G	7(d)	-140.7	158.3	299.1	17.6	0.938	0.0959	0.996	0.424

Fig.8. MOD2 output “normal” waveforms captured at different operating conditions for TIA settings 1 (TS1), (a)-(d) and for TIA setting 2 (TS2), (e)-(h), and different SOA gain operating conditions (a) OC_A, (b) OC_B, (c) OC_C, (d) OC_D, (e) OC_E, (f) OC_F, (g) OC_G, (h) OC_H. Horizontal-axis is Time in Samples (6.25 ps/Sample). The red curve depicts the envelope formed by the pulse peak values of the sequence. I_{SOA} : SOA drive current.

Section III.A, confirming without a doubt that there is minimal dependence in the NLAf shape from the SOA’s recovery time.

It should be noted that the experimentally measured noise contribution of the activation function can be seamlessly incorporated into the training of the proposed DL application and still yield high-accuracy performance, following the approach described in [34], [42]–[44].

C. Opto-electronic-optical (OEO) NLAf

In pure multi-layer PNN the output signal from the activation unit should be in the optical domain, feeding in this way the next neural layer. The TIA of the proposed circuit generates a high output voltage, providing sufficient power for transforming the signal back into the optical domain using a low V_{pi} appropriate modulator [45] technology and employing a GSSG probe for capturing the entire RF signal, reaching up to $0.9 V_{pp}$. However, due to the availability of only a GS probe and a LiNbO3 analog MZM with a 20 GHz 3 dB bandwidth requiring 6 V for pi phase shift, an additional RF driver with a 40 GHz 3-dB bandwidth was used, scenario B in Fig. 2, in the

setup. The optical signal used to feed MOD2 was emitted by LD3 at 1550 nm with 14 dBm output power. The operation point of MOD2 was controlled by a DC Bias supply to ensure operation at the quadrature point. The output of MOD2 carrying the information/shape of the electrical TIA output, was then recorded with the RTO through a 70 GHz bandwidth PD. Careful selection of the output voltage from the driver and the biasing point of the modulator ensured the operation of the modulator strictly in the linear regime.

Figure 8 shows the waveforms captured at the output of the second modulator when the “normal” sequence is injected into the SOA for the eight different operation conditions. Fig. 8(a)-(d) present the results for TS1, while Fig. 8(e)-(h) correspond to TS2. Figure 9 displays the output waveforms captured for the “inverse” injected waveform under the same operation conditions as in Fig. 8. Again Fig. 9(a)-(d) corresponds to TS1, and Fig. 9(e)-(h) corresponds to TS2. By comparing all waveforms in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 with their corresponding ones in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, it is evident that the transition from low to high values, and vice versa occurs more

Fig. 9. (a) MOD2 output “inverse” waveforms captured at different operating conditions for TIA settings 1 (TS1), (a)-(d) and for TIA setting 2 (TS2), (e)-(h), and different SOA gain operating conditions (a) OC_A, (b) OC_B, (c) OC_C, (d) OC_D, (e) OC_E, (f) OC_F, (g) OC_G, (h) OC_H. Horizontal-axis is Time in Samples (6.25 ps/Sample). The red curve depicts the envelope formed by the pulse peak values of the sequence. I_{SOA} : SOA drive current.

Fig. 10. Complete optical unit output measured for “normal” black-squares and the “inverse” waveforms red-circles for TIA settings 1 (TS1) (a)-(d) and TIA settings 2 (TS2) (e)-(h) and different SOA gain operating conditions. (a) OC_A, (b) OC_B, (c) OC_C, (d) OC_D, (e) OC_E, (f) OC_F, (g) OC_G, (h) OG_H. The blue line represents the sigmoid fitting on equation (1) for the combined normal and inverse points.

abruptly in the optical-electrical-optical NLAf due to the sequential application of the sigmoid and the sinusoidal transfer functions from the MZM. Additionally, the output voltage swing is an order of magnitude lower due to the absence of an amplifier after the EO conversion of the signal and the operation of the MZM with limited voltage targeting exploitation of the linear part of the transfer function only.

The red curves in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 indicate the envelope of the peak amplitude of the 32 levels used for the extraction of the OEO NLAf. Once again, the input power points for the calculation of the NLAf are taken from the input waveforms of Fig. 3(a) and Fig. 4(a). Following the same rationale as in Fig. 5, Fig. 9 presents the scattering points at the final output of the circuit in relation to the points from the input waveforms for both the “normal” and “inverse” sequences in the same graph. Fig. 10(a)-(d) displays the superposition of the points for OC_A to OC_D, while Fig. 10(e)-(h) represent the operation conditions OC_E to OC_H. The blue line is the curve fitting of the combined “normal” and “inverse” points, corresponding to the logistic sigmoid function defined by equation (1). The fitting parameters for all curves are displayed in Table III. The R^2 values of the sigmoid fitting exceed 0.98 in all cases, indicating a high level of confidence in the chosen function. The fitted curves are grouped for TS1 in Fig. 11(a), while Fig. 11(b) shows the corresponding curves for TS2. For OC_A, the upper and lower peak amplitudes are 4.4 mV and 27.2 mV, respectively, resulting in a total voltage swing of 22.8 mV. The

10% and 90% points of the activation function correspond to input peak power values of 0.73 mW and 1.19 mW, respectively, resulting in a transition width of ΔP equal to 0.46 mW. In the case of OC_C, where the SOA current is increased to 90 mA, the lower amplitude decreases to 4.0 mV, the upper amplitude limit is reduced to 27.70 mV, and the total voltage swing slightly increases to 23.6 mV. The 10% and 90% points of the NLAf correspond to 0.77 mW and 1.14 mW peak power, resulting in a transition width of only 0.369 mW. For OC_B, the lower limit increases to 5.8 mV, while the upper limit decreases to 26.7 mV, resulting in a total voltage swing of 20.56 mV. The 10% and 90% of the NLAf corresponds to 0.66 mW and 1.66mW and respectively, resulting in a transition width of 0.70 mW. Finally, for OC_D, the lower amplitude increases to 5.6 mV, while the upper is decreased to 26.7 mV for a total voltage swing of 21.53 mV. The 10 – 90 % transition points of the NLAf are moved to the 0.72 mW and 1.28 mW respectively for a ΔP equal to 0.553 mW.

For TS2 and OC_E, the upper and lower peak amplitudes are 4.0 mV and 25 mV with a total voltage swing of 21.5 mV, the 10% and 90% output of the transfer function corresponds to 0.63 mW and 1.20 mW input peak power resulting in a 10%-90% transition ΔP of 0.575 mW. By increasing the SOA bias current to 90 mA (OC_G) the lower amplitude remains to 4.0 mV and the upper amplitude is increased to 25.6 mV for a total voltage swing of 21.6 mV. The 10% and 90% of the TF corresponds to 0.69 mW and 1.12 mW peak power and the ΔP

TABLE III Sigmoid fitting parameters of the OEO TF (MOD 2 output)

Conditions	A_1	A_2	A_2-A_1	X_0	d_x	R^2	10%-90% ΔP [mw]
OC_A	4.413	27.234	22.821	0.967	0.105	0.986	0.46
OC_B	5.813	26.374	20.561	1.014	0.160	0.985	0.70
OC_C	4.089	27.708	23.619	0.956	0.084	0.982	0.369
OC_D	5.637	26.790	21.153	1.005	0.126	0.984	0.553
OC_E	4.097	25.692	21.595	0.921	0.131	0.987	0.575
OC_F	4.487	25.302	20.815	0.915	0.229	0.988	1
OC_G	4.053	25.665	21.612	0.911	0.097	0.983	0.42
OC_H	4.593	25.222	20.629	0.923	0.178	0.988	0.79

Fig. 11. (a) Complete optical unit Transfer function sigmoid fitting equation (1) for different operating conditions (ISOA and CW) for TIA settings 1 (TS1) and (b) TIA settings 2 (TS2).

is decreased to 0.42 mW. For OC_F the lower amplitude limit is increased at 4.4 mV and the upper limit is decreased at 25.3 mV, whereas the 10% of the NLAFF correspond to 0.41 mW and 1.41 resulting a ΔP of 1.0 mW. Finally for OC_H the lower level is increased to 4.5 mV, while the upper one is decreased to 25.22 mV for a total voltage swing of 20.62 mV. The 10 to 90 % points of the NLAFF are moved now to 0.53 mW and 1.31 mW, respectively with a ΔP of 0.78 mW.

The key conclusions from all fitted curves in Fig. 11 is that again TS1 provides slightly better voltage swing versus TS2. This is not so emphasized as at the output of the TIA since the driver modulator is compensating part of the gain difference. However again TS2 provides better symmetry both relative to the 1 mW input threshold and the 15 mV symmetry value. Also, the fitted sigmoid in all cases is superimposed on a small ~ 5 mW pedestal that is due to the operation of the MZM in the linear regime only. By playing with the modulator bias it was possible to get a perfect zero level, but then the peak power of the pulses was distorted from the high nonlinear regime of the MZM. The steepest transition is observed for OC_B, where the fitted curve is approximating very good a step function as the ΔP is only 0.37 mW. This is the sharpest slope for all examined operation conditions and configurations of the examined circuit. In contrast OC_F provides a more linear operation, with the ΔP enhanced to 1 mW now. This comes in agreement with the results at the output of the TIA where OC_C was delivering the steepest and OC_F the more linear transfer functions. The trend though of lower ΔP with the inclusion of the optical modulator for transferring the signal in the optical domain is clear for all scenarios. All above results confirm that the proposed circuit is capable to provide a sigmoid NLAFF with variable steepness and voltage swing by interplaying with the TIA's settings and the SOA's gain adjusted either by changing the biasing current and/or by injected an external CW signal. Any non-linearities and the additional power consumption coming from the driver modulator could be avoided if the LiNbO3 MOD2 could be replaced with a push pull BTO based modulator requiring only 2.9 Vmm at low frequencies [45].

It should be noted that the assessment of the OEO NLAFF circuit under random input sequences, similar to the procedure of Section III.B, was omitted. This decision was based on the dependency of the modulator's response solely on the input voltage. Consequently, the inclusion of these additional results would not contribute any novel information.

IV. DISCUSSION

Harnessing the advantages of photonic neural networks necessitates operational rates in the tens of GHz regime for both linear and non-linear components of the photonic accelerator [24]. This imposes strenuous requirements on the NLAFF circuitry, which must operate in the tens of GHz regime, provide the required non-linear behavior within a low-input power envelope, and supply sufficient output power to drive the subsequent neural layer [46].

In this context, all-optical deployments offer a direct method for implementing NLAFF operation, achieving full activation within the optical domain and negating the need for costly electro-optic conversions. However, they often require high input powers to trigger nonlinear effects, leading to the use of active optical amplification and resulting in prohibitive power consumption. Additionally, when deployed within cascaded multi-layer networks, the inherent high losses impose further limitations on the overall performance and energy efficiency of the system [13], [15], [20], [23], [30].

These performance limitations have led to intensive research in EO implementations that utilize a cascade of EO components to achieve non-linear activation and drive subsequent photonic neural network layers [12], [14] [46], [47]. While these approaches alleviate the high-input power requirements of all-optical implementations, the two main physical mechanisms employed—electrical gain and optical pumping of the output neuron—impose a three-folded operational trade-off between analog bandwidth, NLAFF input sensitivity, and energy efficiency [48].

Following this approach, [46], uses a PD and passive TIA to directly drive an intensity modulator, avoiding electrical amplification. However, this method requires a highly sensitive MRR, necessitating active control, which adversely affects the system's energy efficiency. In another strategy, [47], proposes a similar architecture but recommends adding an active TIA after the PD for electrical amplification. While this reduces the sensitivity required for the cascaded MRR in EO conversion, it's essential to note that the MRR still needs active control for operation. Additionally, in both cases, the NLAFF unit operates at 1 GHz, constrained by the free-carrier injection effect of the forward-biased MRR to approximately 6 GHz. These limitations impede the scalability of these units for large-scale applications. In a more recent approach [14], an OEO NLAFF unit employs a balanced PD for OE conversion, an active TIA for nonlinearity in the electrical domain, and an external MZM for EO conversion. This design achieves operation at 10 GHz with an energy consumption of 36 pJ/NOP. [12] presents an OEO approach where a portion of the optical power is converted to the electrical domain through a PD and an active TIA. This electrical signal then modulates the remaining optical power through an on-chip MZM, eliminating the need for an extra laser source and operating at 10 GHz with an energy consumption of 40 pJ/NOP. However, this approach's cascading capability is hindered by the losses from the conversion process for each activation, that necessitate high optical power resulting in increased power consumption.

Our approach stands out from the previous demonstrations due to the inclusion of the SOA before the UTC-PD. This addition aims to amplify weak optical input power from the

preceding NN layer and introduce extra nonlinearity through SOA gain control. The presence of the SOA makes the circuit compatible with low power signals expected in multi-layer PNNs. This is confirmed in [36], where successful reception of 32Gb/s PRBS31 NRZ signals with clear eye opening was achieved even for -19 dBm input power. The proposed NLAF circuitry operates at 10 GHz rates but has the capability to reach up to 40 GHz, potentially supporting low input power envelopes [36], to provide non-linear behavior and ultimately supplying enough output power to drive a subsequent low V_{pi} modulator [45]. These metrics position the device to be comparable, if not superior, to the state-of-the-art OEO approaches discussed above, which achieve up to 10 GHz operation and 37.5 pJ/NOP [14].

V. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this paper presents a detailed circuit description and experimental results of an OE circuit capable of providing a non-linear sigmoid activation function with variable steepness for PNNs. The circuit consists of an InP O-band SOA co-integrated with a high-speed UTC-PD where the output is wire bonded to a TIA chip fabricated at 55 nm SiGe-BiCMOS technology. The overall performance of the circuit was evaluated through the injection of two 10 GHz custom mirrored 32-level patterns to identify any patterning effects arising from the limited recovery time of the SOA. The results confirm the effectiveness of the circuit by demonstrating a variable NLAF through the interplay of the TIA's settings and the adjustment of the SOA's gain using either the biasing current or an external CW signal. In total eight different combinations of operating conditions were identified as the most suitable ones for producing a sigmoid NLAF with the corresponding output waveforms, achieving the desired sigmoid shape with very high accuracy and an energy efficiency of 36 pJ/bit. The half voltage swing at the output of the TIA varied between 326 mV and 452 mV, while the transition points from 10% to 90% were adjusted between 0.58 mW and 1.65 mW for the steepest and more linear cases respectively. The circuit's performance was further evaluated through the injection of three 10 GHz 30-level pulse sequences with random peak power, validating the sigmoid fitting for the NLAF and confirming shape adjustability with varying operational conditions. Furthermore, the paper explores the conversion of the electrical signal back to the optical domain through an external modulator. The activation function of the optical waveform is of a sigmoid shape again, with the results revealing an even steeper transition with the 10% to 90% transition reduced now to 0.37 mW. The sigmoid slope could be configured also to more linear response with a 10% to 90% width of 1 mW. The S₂₁ measurements of the NLAF OE circuit indicate that the same circuit is capable of operating at 30 GHz or even higher, while the high output voltage from the TIA is capable of driving the weighing element of the next neural layer. Overall, the experimental results confirmed that the proposed circuit provided a sigmoid NLAF with variable steepness and voltage swing, offering very high flexibility in shaping the circuit's response at very high speed. The findings of this work contribute to the development of OE circuits for applications in PNNs and signal processing systems. Finally, this work enhances the current portfolio of photonic

analog-derived activation function circuitry, opening new research opportunities in studying NN training algorithms and methods for harnessing their performance advantages in specific applications [49].

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